

Gavin Menzies and his 1421: The Year China Discovered the World

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*To the memory of Gavin Menzies (1937-2020)
for his perseverance in continuing the project
on China's global reach and cultural influence.*

Summary

The appearance of the book *1421: The Year in which China Discovered the World*, has generated —especially in Western academia— a bitter controversy about the role played by Chinese cartography during the sixth expedition commanded by Admiral Zheng He, together with Admirals Zhou Man, Hong Bao, Zhou Wen and Yang Qing between 1421-1423. The certainty of the results about this historical process would blow up the deep-rooted Eurocentrism and the apology for the discoveries that for centuries has placed the field of Western culture as the epicenter of world development. This article analyzes the scope outlined by the English author Gavin Menzies (1937-2020), his detractors and the currents of anti-Chinese thought today regarding the present work.

Key words: world cartography, Western culture, Eurocentrism, historical process.

Resumen

La aparición del libro *1421: El año en que China descubrió el mundo*, ha generado —sobre todo en el ámbito académico occidental—, una enconada polémica sobre el papel ejercido por la cartografía china durante la sexta expedición comandada por el almirante Zheng He, junto con los almirantes Zhou Man, Hong Bao, Zhou Wen y Yang Qing entre 1421-1423. La certidumbre de los resultados acerca de este proceso histórico haría saltar por los aires el tan arraigado eurocentrismo y la apología de los descubrimientos que durante siglos ha colocado el ámbito de la cultura occidental como epicentro del desarrollo mundial. En este artículo se analiza el alcance trazado por el autor inglés Gavin Menzies (1937-2020), sus detractores y las corrientes de pensamiento antichino en la actualidad respecto de la presente obra.

Palabras claves: cartografía mundial, cultura occidental, eurocentrismo, proceso histórico.

A very polemic book

The work of the Englishman Gavin Menzies (1937-2020), which he rightly titled *1421: The Year China Discovered the World*, has had and still has followers and detractors; something very common in works that blow up conceptions rooted in a part of the documentation taken as true and that now, with new contributions, bring to light the results of the sixth expedition commanded by Zheng He, together with admirals Zhou Man, Hong Bao, Zhou Wen and Yang Qing between 1421-1423. Fully aware of the significance of his research, the author himself considers:

My research confirmed that, in fact, several Chinese fleets had made voyages of exploration in the early days of the 15th century. The last and most important of these four fleets comprising an immense army departed in early 1421. The last surviving ships returned to China in the summer and fall of 1423. There was no record of where they had traveled in the intervening years, but maps showed that they had not only rounded the Cape of Good Hope and crossed the Atlantic to chart the islands I had seen on Pizzigano's map of 1424 but had also gone on to explore Antarctica and the Arctic, North and South America, and had crossed the Pacific to Australia. They had solved the problem of calculating latitude and longitude and had mapped the earth and the firmament with equal accuracy.¹

The above synthesizes the central core of this work: to fulfill the mandate of Emperor Zhu Di (1360-1424) to achieve total certainty of the globe through cartography and thus expand the knowledge of the world as part of the very policy opened at this stage of the Ming dynasty. The version analyzed is in PDF format prepared by Patricio Barros, with the collaboration of Sergio Barros (2002), which is characterized by a writing in Spanish very attached to the grammar and syntax of the English language, so it would merit a critical edition in Spanish language that includes a total revision of the text, the adequate use of the writing and syntax, the correct use of punctuation marks and in certain cases of the spelling. It has also been checked against the English version published by Bantam New Edition, 2003. In general, the initial translation is valid insofar as it assumes the author's colloquial sense to take the reader by the hand, in a pleasant way, through a highly complex and controversial subject, where the research methods used are combined

¹ *Op.cit.*: 16, in <https://www.academia.edu/search?utf8=%E2%9C%93&q=1421+El+a%C3%B1o+en+que+China+descubri%C3%B3+el+mundo>

with the evidence that makes it possible to move from the strictly hypothetical to the demonstrative. During the development of the work Menzies addresses a subject that obviously attempts against the deep-rooted Eurocentrism settled in the mentalities of experts, professors, and researchers, as well as of many students of the western hemisphere. In this sense he comments:

Although the Western world is generally silent about the origin of these extraordinary maps of the world, already accurate in terms of both latitude and longitude, the inscription engraved on the stele erected by Zheng He in commemoration of his voyages shows whose merit it is: "And now, as a result of the voyages, distances and courses between distant lands can be calculated". It was another imposing achievement of the Chinese fleets, an achievement whose light should shine like a beacon in the annals of world history. Far from it, however, that light would be extinguished and forgotten, along with the discovery of America, Australia, Antarctica, and the Arctic; Europeans would claim for themselves the glory that should have been attributed to the great Chinese admirals and their fleets. It would be the Portuguese who would lead this European wave of exploration and colonization. And it would be they, more than any other nation, who would benefit from China's hard-won knowledge of the oceans and the new lands beyond them.²

Likewise, it also goes against the limited vision of many historians who self-limit the sources to written texts and everything outside that scheme becomes "prehistory" or lends itself to all kinds of doubts, mistrust, and suspicions. However, Menzies combines the hypothetico-deductive, analytical-synthetic, and comparative methods, with the full range of useful sources to replace what is repeatedly complained about during his research:

Mandarin Liu Daxia, a high-ranking official in the Ministry of War, seized upon the records, stating that "San Bao's [Zheng He] expeditions to the Western Ocean consumed a great deal of money and grain, and moreover the people who met their deaths there can be counted by many thousands." [...] all the records of those expeditions-"misleading exaggerations of strange things far removed from the testimony of the eyes and ears of the people"-should be burned. Liu then calmly informed the Minister of War that the diaries and records of Zheng He's expeditions had been "lost."³

Faced with such a vacuum of information, the author turns to the sources of historians, anthropologists, archaeologists, biologists, linguists, mineralogists, geologists, travelers, oral memory, archives, fieldwork; in short, he uses the

² *Ibid.*: 360-361.

³ *Ibid.*: 60.

information he considers useful for the fulfillment of his objectives and discards all possible false leads. He relies especially on his extensive experience and expertise as a retired Royal Navy officer to critically study various maps and nautical charts, which, together with his knowledge of land and space cartography, winds, sea currents and maritime orientation, allows him to reconstruct the great void of information. For this reason, he states that:

My assertions about Chinese voyages in the "lost years" of 1421 to 1423 are based on the authenticity of the maps of Kangnido, Piri Reis, Jean Rotz, Cantino, Waldseemüller and Pizzigano. No one has ever questioned their veracity. The Vinland map was questioned in the past, but, as I have already shown [...], I believe it passes the test of authenticity. The Piri Reis, Jean Rotz and Cantino maps represent the entire southern hemisphere, covering tens of millions of square kilometers of ocean, thousands of islands, and tens of thousands of kilometers of coastline from the Antarctic to Ecuador. The lands they show could only have been mapped by fleets that had sailed the southern hemisphere before the European voyages of discovery, and those fleets could only have been Chinese.⁴

But beyond the research procedures, his reflections during the search for clues and intellectual disquisitions, the author also places great emphasis on the evidence for a Chinese presence long before the visits of Europeans, who traveled oriented by previous maps. Among this evidence are:

- The maps of Pizzigano (1424), Fra Mauro (1459), Cantino (1502), Caverio (1505), Waldseemüller (1507), Piri Reis (1513) and Jean Rotz (1542), which represent the entire world mapped before the Europeans set sail.
- The commemorative stelae erected in 1430-1431 in Liu-Chia-Chang and Chiang-su where it is stated that Zhen He reached three thousand large and small countries. But engraved stone stelae were also erected in Sri Lanka, the Indian Ocean, the Congo Delta, the Cape Verde Islands, North America, Brazil, and New Zealand.
- Chinese pictorial records (*The Illustrated Archive of Strange Countries* or *I Yü Thu Chih*), from 1430, showing lions and elephants in India; zebras and giraffes in Africa; armadillos, jaguars, and Mylodon in South America.
- The determination of longitude during the voyage is crucial for maritime orientation and cartographic accuracy.
- Areas of the world mapped: the Indian Ocean; South America and the Antarctic; North America and the North Atlantic; the Far East; and Australasia. The terrestrial and astronomical maps produced in Asia: in the *Wu Pei Chi* (c. 1422)

⁴ *Ibid.*: 425-426.

the Chinese accept that it contains information contributed by Zheng He; in the Kangnido map (1402-1473) appears the Indian Ocean and islands, coasts of East Africa and the courses to be followed in Asia, the Orient, southern and western Africa, including the Azores; in the Astronomical Map or Mao Kun (c. 1422), the North Star is located compared to the Southern Cross and Alpha Centauri; and in the *Astronomical Map* or *Mao Kun* (c. 1488), the North Star is located compared to the Southern Cross and Alpha Centauri; and in Matteo Ricci's Globe (c. 1588), Australia is drawn when Fra Ricci was in China.

- Chinese and Asian settlers encountered by early European explorers.
- Local people's accounts (in Africa, America, Asia, and Australia) of Chinese, or "yellow men", before the voyages of the European "discoverers".
- Artwork depicting foreigners prior to Europeans (Australia, and Mexico).
- Petroglyphs (rock art) pre-dating Europeans (Australia, Mexico, and North America).
- Plants originating from one continent transported to another. For example: From China to Australia: lotus and papyrus; to North America: rice, poppy seeds, Keteleria, roses (*Rosa laevigata*); to the Pacific Islands: blackberries; and to South America: rice. From South America to China: corn; to Southeast Asia: corn; to New Zealand: kumara (sweet potato variety); to the Pacific Islands: yam, sweet potato; to Australia: 74 species; and the Philippines: potatoes, corn.
- Animals originating from one continent found in another. For example: Asian chickens in South America; horses in North America, Australia, and Mexico; Chinese dogs in Mexico, South America, South Africa, Southeast Asia, Pacific, Falklands, New Zealand and Tahiti; sea otters in New Zealand; as well as lions, elephants and tigers from India; giraffes, rhinoceroses, ostriches and zebras from Africa; and kangaroos from Australia in the Chinese Emperor's Zoo.
- Mining and other activities encountered by early Europeans. Mining and processing of gold, lead, copper, cast bronze, iron, and coal. Pre-Columbian metallurgy, lacquering and dyeing in Mesoamerica, the area of which already appears on Waldseemüller's map.
- Wrecks of very old, large, and unidentified shipwrecks found along the path of the Chinese fleets.
- Artifacts and votive offerings such as early Ming porcelain in eastern and southern Africa; Australia; the Pacific coast of America; and Mexico; in the Philippines and Indonesia Magellan's descriptions refer to silk-clad rulers who possessed early Ming dishes. Various objects such as a bronze lion with Chinese features in East Africa; the statue in the Azores found by the first Europeans who landed there; the onyx beetles, Shao Lin head, jade Buddha,

and Laozi statuette in Australia; the serpentine duck and Chinese steatite statuette in New Zealand; for example.

These and other examples that are observed in the development of the work and then synthesized in the Appendices, have been subjected to a detailed demonstrative process that exceeds the level of hypothetical abstraction and open new interstices for the continuity of the investigation. The delicate unraveling of the skein of problems that the author gradually solves makes it possible for him to state the following:

As brave and determined as they were, Columbus, Dias, Da Gama, Magellan, Cook and the rest of the European explorers set sail armed with maps that showed them the way to their destinations. They owed it all to the first explorers, the Chinese, in their epic voyages of 1421-1423. The fortune of the Europeans was paralleled by the misfortune of China, whose Forbidden City was devastated by fire on May 9, 1421. Europeans would now rediscover almost the entire world, hitherto known at first hand only to the Chinese and Niccolò dei Conti. The maps, ships and ocean navigation systems used by the great European explorers owed much to Henry the Navigator and his brother Dom Pedro; but they owed an even greater debt to the Chinese emperor, Zhu Di, and his brave and expert eunuch admirals, Zheng He, Zhou Man, Hong Bao, Zhou Wen, and Yang Qing.⁵

However, accepting these results is obvious to some and very difficult or unheard of for others. Therefore, in the face of the accumulation of evidence derived from an arduous investigative process Menzies points out:

There is no doubt that these statements will be received with surprise; but if a dispassionate view is taken, it will be seen that there is nothing illogical about them. The Chinese enjoyed an older and richer maritime tradition than the Europeans. When Zhu Di's fleets set sail in 1421, they had at least six centuries of oceanic exploration and astronomical navigation behind them; when Días and Magellan set sail, on the other hand, the Portuguese lacked the means to navigate accurately south of the equator.⁶

In this sense, a prestigious Argentine specialist based in Mexico, Enrique Dussel, has published *La China (1421-1800) (Razones para cuestionar el eurocentrismo / Reasons to question Eurocentrism)*,⁷ where he relies on the results of Menzies' work to affirm:

⁵ *Ibid.*: 414.

⁶ *Ibid.*: 427.

⁷ See Dussel, 2004: 6-13.

The traditional "Eurocentric" position believed that Europe had certain very ancient potentialities (Max Weber goes back to the origin of Christianity and even to the thought of the prophets of Israel), which, crossing the so-called "Middle Ages", burst with creative force into Modernity. Europe had long sought to prove its cultural "superiority" over other cultures (even over Hindustani, Chinese or Islamic cultures, and thus had given rise to capitalism, a historical question to which M. Weber devotes extensive works).⁸

The present work of Gavin Menzies, demonstrates that China was centuries ahead of Europe from the political, commercial, technological and scientific point of view, by means of diverse proofs on the maritime route headed by Zhen He, thanks to its oceanic experiences of more than eight hundred years in the Indian Ocean and the western Pacific, and by the development reached in astronomy, cartography, instruments of measurement of latitude and longitude, type of boats, food, tonnage and in organization.

Against Menzies and 1421

However, to be in tune with the deep-rooted Eurocentrism, when Jaime Mateu Pérez reviews the presentation of Gavin Menzies' book in Spain,⁹ he recognizes that the author "has knowledge that none of the great sinologists of the intellectual world has. The knowledge contributed by forty years circumnavigating the globe. And, therefore, the knowledge of nautical, astronomy, winds, sea currents and the experience derived from having visited more than 120 countries in which he has searched incessantly for remains that confirm his hypothesis". In other words, he reduces the work to a hypothetical formulation. He also considers him "a neophyte in the subject of East Asian history" but does not point out that the author consulted the main European and Asian authorities on this subject during each stage of the research process, so that for Mateu "it is difficult to evaluate the veracity or falsehoods provided by this work". Among the possible gaps of the author "does not highlight what is the underlying reason for the change of attitude of the emperors in reference to travel or the influence of the mandarins in constant struggle with the power of the eunuchs", which indicates that he overlooked the entire first part of the book where Menzies explains in detail this process, from the international opening of Emperor Zhu Di and the great support given by the eunuchs in the seizure of power, to the rise to power of Zhu Gaozhi, his son, the support of the mandarins and the policy of closure to the exterior.

⁸ *Ibid.*: 6.

⁹ See Mateu, 2006: 329-330.

Another author who circumscribes the subject to the American continent is Robert Finlay professor emeritus of the University of Arkansas, specialized in modern European history and history mundial in his text "How not to (re)write world history: Gavin Menzies and the Chinese discovery of America".¹⁰ With sustained sarcasm he tries to refute each of Menzies' points of view and comes to the defense of the much-demoralized Eurocentrism, from the American cultural paradigm where America (USA) is equal to The World, a cliché that Menzies himself had foreseen and warned about. In this case, with evident burlesque tone concludes:

Still, it may have some pedagogical value in world history courses. By assigning selections from the book to high school students and undergraduates, it could serve as an outstanding example of how not to (re)write world history. Instructors seeking to provide light relief to a lengthy subject could also encourage students to compete in nominating the most peculiar or amusing passage in the book.¹¹

The last part of the concluding reflection I do not reproduce as disrespectful to the author and to the legacy of the Chinese admirals, but it is not a bad idea to put Menzies' work in the hands of students, for they are fully entitled to make their own interpretations and conclusions.

Similarly, Isidro Ot Padilla's¹² point of view also reduces a global issue to the problems of America. Therefore, he believes that "the real merit of Menzies is to have brought together, albeit loosely and with little rigor, many of the interdisciplinary clues and information suggesting a pre-contact and to have combined them in a single attractive and entertaining story for the general public. Beyond this, we consider the thesis, for the moment, inconclusive". Everything indicates that either Padilla did not understand anything or simply did not read the work, since Menzies does not limit himself to what he knows inside out in his field, but resorts to with all rigor and depth, to give a solution to each one of the unknowns that are presented, he relates them, analyzes them, identifies the evidence, interprets them and constantly evaluates them in their historical context. It is for this reason that Menzies proposes: "In trying to reconstruct the voyages that the fleets had made, the first thing I had to do was to put myself in the shoes of the Chinese admirals.

¹⁰ See Finlay, 2004: 229-242.

¹¹ *Ibid.*: 242

¹² See Ot, 2017: 28-29.

And there was no better way to do this than to sail in their footsteps, just as I had done as a young officer aboard the Royal Navy's Newfoundland".¹³

As part of the current fierce anti-Russian and anti-Chinese political campaign, authors Greg Melleuish, Konstantin Sheiko and Stephen Brown, from the University of Wollongong in Australia, publish a virulent article against the works of Anatoly Fomenko¹⁴ and Gavin Menzies,¹⁵ where they try to nullify or reduce to zero the ideas of these two authors as follows:

One of the most important developments in the production of history in the early 21st century has been the ability of "weird history" or "pseudo history" to have a major impact on the public sphere. Pseudo history mimics professional history in the way it is presented to the public, but its arguments defy any reasonable assessment of the evidence. [Here], we examine the phenomenon of pseudohistory through a consideration of its origins in travelers' tales and its current manifestation with special reference to two practitioners: Anatolii Fomenko and Gavin Menzies. One can attribute much of its popular success to its ability to appeal to both democracy and nationalism, and to make effective use of the new media, especially the Internet.¹⁶

In the case of the work at hand (*1421...*) they try to compare it to a science fiction story to neutralize or reduce to absurdity all the investigative results. In this way they refer:

Menzies is essentially promoting a fantastic traveler's tale about the Chinese fleet, a modern equivalent of the extraordinary stories that appear in Herodotus. His special achievement is to make his account of the Zheng He voyages appear to be not only plausible, but also to cloak it with a layer of scholarly respectability. He has several techniques that enable him to achieve that goal. The most important thing to keep in mind is that Menzies has considerable freedom because much of the written evidence regarding Zheng He has been destroyed. This means that he is free to speculate using a range of other evidence, especially maps and a variety of physical and scientific evidence, that relates to DNA. In the absence of other forms of documentary

¹³ *Op.cit.*: 84.

¹⁴ Although the work of this author is not the subject of our commentary, the Dr. Anatoly Fomenko is an Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Academician of the Russian Academy of Natural Sciences, Academician of the International Academy of Sciences of Higher Education, Doctor of Physics and Mathematics, Professor, Head of the Department of Mathematics and Mechanics of Moscow State University. So, he is not just any author.

¹⁵ See Melleuish, Sheiko, and Brown, 2009: 1484-1495.

¹⁶ *Op. cit.*: 1484.

evidence maps and other forms of pictorial evidence become the crucial form of written evidence for Menzies.¹⁷

Once again, together with the absence of the slightest professional ethics, even the disrespect for the contribution of Herodotus (484-425 B.C.E.) in his time, in relation to the historical account and the sources he used, the unrestricted attachment to the "written evidence", as if this were always the bearer of the truth; they confuse the "techniques that allow him to achieve this objective" with the combination of research methods that the author uses to replace the vacuum left by the mandarin Liu Daxia. However, they contradict themselves, because indeed, a very important part of the evidence with which Menzies works, are cartographic documents that were drawn and written by their respective authors and copyists; and the texts of the maps are important evidence to decipher the names of the mapped territories.

But Gavin Menzies does not detract from the heroics of the European seafarers in his time, but rather puts them in their place with respect to the earlier work of Zhen He's fleet. After being convinced of the accumulation of information studied, he proposes:

Magellan, Dias, Da Gama, and Cabral were pilots and sailors of great skill; they were also brave and determined men, with impressive leadership skills; but none of them actually discovered "new lands". When they set sail, each of them carried a map showing where they were going. All their "discoveries" had been made by the Chinese almost a century earlier.

Nor did Christopher Columbus "discover" America. Far from setting sail filled with dread at the prospect of his fleet hurtling over the edge of the world, he knew exactly where he was going, as can be seen from excerpts from his ship's logbooks, written while he was still in the middle of the Atlantic. [...]

Columbus' real legacy to posterity is not the discovery of America, but that of the systems of wind circulation in the Atlantic, which he so brilliantly analyzed and exploited in his later voyages. Knowledge of the patterns of those winds and currents would prove invaluable in the preparation and execution of the voyages that would lead to the colonization of America in later centuries.¹⁸

¹⁷ *Ibid*: 1498. For example, other authors maintain that conception such as Fritze, 2011: 12-19; y Henige, 2008: 354-372.

¹⁸ *Op.cit.*: 402 y 411.

That is why rightly claiming honors to those who deserve honors is a way to break the silence and complicity with the advances achieved early on by China. In this sense he stresses:

To assert the primacy of Chinese exploration of the New World and Australia is not tantamount to denigrating the achievements or memory of Days, Columbus, Magellan and Cook. The exploits of these able and brave men will never be forgotten, but it is time to honor other men who have been left to languish in the shadows for too long. Those extraordinary Chinese admirals rounded the Cape of Good Hope sixty-six years before Días, crossed the Strait of Magellan ninety-eight years before Magellan himself, and explored Australia three centuries before Captain Cook, Antarctica, and the Arctic four centuries before the first Europeans, and America seventy years before Columbus. The great admirals Zheng He, Hong Bao, Zhou Man, Zhou Wen, and Yang Qing also deserve to be remembered and praised, for they were the first, as well as the bravest and boldest of all. Those who followed them, however great their achievements, merely sailed in their wake.¹⁹

Along with the works published on paper and electronically, the author had a website in English, Spanish and Polish,²⁰ to follow up on the subject, disseminate new results, publish texts and maps, and this has undoubtedly influenced audiovisual filmmakers as motivation and information for various creations on the screen.

The Saga of Zhen He and His Admirals

In this globalized world and with the impetuous development of mass media, the complicit silence of Eurocentrism is transformed into image and sound through a significant number of documentaries available on the YouTube platform. We can refer to about 28 audiovisuals, including documentaries, cartoons, and news, 3 of them in several parts with very different approaches and scopes. It is very important that they are available in the three major world languages: Chinese, Spanish and English; and also French, with more than 274 million speakers. At the beginning of July 2020, these materials already had some 6,452,986 visualizations, to which we should add the collective visualizations; particularly on computers, since on cell phones and tablets it tends to be of an individual nature.

Although the filmography revolves around the Chinese fleets commanded by Admiral Zhen He, the thematic fields are very varied according to the interests of

¹⁹ *Ibid.*: 335.

²⁰ See <https://www.gavinmenzies.net/>

the filmmakers and the points of view expressed on the screen. One of them addresses the impressive technological difference between *Columbus' Ships vs. Zheng He's Treasure Ships* (2007) through a comparative reference of the large Chinese junks with respect to the small European caravels. Another, for comparative purposes as *Columbus, De Gama and Zheng He! Sailors of the 15th century. Crash Course: World History #21* (2012), highlights the feat of the Chinese fleet in relation to later voyages led by Christopher Columbus and Vasco da Gama. Others narrow the worldview addressed by Gavin Menzies' work such as *Did China Discover America? The Voyages of Zheng He* (2018) and *Who Reached America Before Columbus* (2018), as they circumscribe the expedition to the American continent with varying opinions on the matter.

Of Chinese production, *Zheng He* (2012) is an animated in three episodes aimed at children and young people to disseminate the figure of the admiral; others are shorter for their newsworthiness as *A photographic exhibition traces the travels of Marco Polo and Zheng He* (2016) through the lens of Michael Yamashita, evokes what was observed by the Venetian traveler of the late thirteenth century and the admiral of the fifteenth century, as reported by CCTV News; also *A model ship of Zheng He's fleet reproduced in Shanghai* (2017) refers it China Xinhua Spanish, to disclose the Ming Fu ship, reproduced and exhibited at the Maritime Museum on the occasion of China's Navigation Day; for its part the Latin American agency teleSUR tv contributes a report entitled *Chinese Empire made naval expeditions long before Europe* (2017) where it associates the construction of large ships in Nanjing and naval expeditions with the maritime silk road.

However, most audiovisuals highlight the figure of the admiral and his fleet, such as *Zheng He: Emperors of the Seas* (2008); *"Zheng He"-The Great Traveler 1405-1433 AD* (2012); *The Treasure Ships* (2012); *Great Voyages: Zhen He* (2013); *Zheng He and His Floating City: when China ruled the oceans* (2014); *Zheng He, Emperor of the Seas* (2014, in four parts); *Canned Stories: The Voyages of Zheng He* (2014); *Zheng He's Art of Collaboration* (2014) in three parts, assesses leadership skills then and compares him to business leaders today; *The Travels of Chinese-Muslim Admiral Zheng He* (2015, in two parts), where he highlights his Arabic name, Mahmoud Shams oud-Din, along with the task of another Chinese-Muslim, Ma Huan, who accompanied the admiral on several of his journeys and recounted his observations on geography, laws, politics, climatic conditions, environment, economy and local customs of the countries visited; *History Documentaries - Documentary on the adventures of Zheng He in the Chinese treasure fleet* (2017); *The maritime adventures of the eunuch admiral Zheng He*

(2017); *Epic voyages of Zheng He, Chinese admiral of the 15th century* (2018); *The Chinese navy mysterious voyages of Admiral Zheng in the S. XIV* (2018) although must have referred to the century XV; *When China ruled the waves (Chinese dynasty documentary)* (2018); *The voyages of Zheng He (The Ming treasure fleet)* (2018); *Zhenghe (Chinese explorer): the facts and his achievements, the unpublished history* (2018); *China (The Voyages of Admiral Zheng He in the 15th Century)* (2018); *The Voyages of Zheng He* (2018); *Voyages of Zheng He (1405-1433)* (2019); and *Zheng He, the crazy story of the great eunuch explorer!* (2020). All focus their attention on the voyages of the Chinese fleets while marking a growing trend toward supporting the findings of Gavin Menzies' work to help dispel doubts of skeptics and mistrust of doubters.

In this way, the polemic work gains relevance and validity, since the great Chinese fleet of the 15th century opened the world path of the *Maritime Silk Road*, left multiple cultural traces in the places where it was and received diverse knowledge, practices, animal and vegetable species to widen the mutual understanding of the visited spaces; jointly, the cartography provided served as a guide to the "European era of discoveries".

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Filmography on Zheng He: (in chronological order)

Columbus's ship vs Zheng He's Treasure ship.

[Los barcos de Colón vs los barcos del Tesoro de Zheng He]

Date: August 26, 2007 (56,392 views)

Synopsis: View of the model in Nanjing at the site of the Ming dynasty shipyard where Admiral Zheng He's ships were built.

Duration: 3:27

Source: <https://www.dailymotion.com/video/x2p5cgx>

Zheng He: Emperors of the Seas.

[Zheng He: Emperadores de los Mares]

Date: 13 January, 2008 (30,757 views)

Duration: 1:57

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K54hxWTIEZo>

Los barcos del Tesoro.

[The treasure ships].

Date: May 17, 2012 (5100 views) Sea Channel.

Duration: 8:56

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DdS3DyvfCNg>

«Zheng He» - *The Great Voyager 1405-1433 AD.*

[«Zheng He» - El gran viajero 1405-1433 AD].

Date: June 9, 2012 (150,731 views).

Synopsis: Zheng He from 1405 to 1433 made 7 voyages with over 1000 soldiers and crew to India and Africa. The great explorer. His voyages were hidden from history and the records were burned. The information of "Zheng He" and his

voyages were discovered in 1930. The Chinese invented a magnetic compass giving them the ability to navigate in hostile environments.

Duration: 5:46

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UPxUZOUUMLI>

Columbus, de Gama, and Zheng He! 15th Century Mariners. Crash Course: World History #21.

[;Colón, De Gama y Zheng He! Marineros del siglo XV. Curso de Choque: Historia Mundial #21].

Date: June 14, 2012 (3,235,081 views)

Synopsis: In this documentary John Green teaches you about the beginning of the so-called Age of Discovery. You've probably heard of Christopher Columbus, who "discovered" America in 1492, but what about Vasco da Gama, how about Zheng He? Columbus gets a bad rap from many modern historians, but it turns out he was important when it comes to world history. That said, he wasn't the only pioneer who plied the seas in the 1400s. In Portugal, Vasco da Gama was busy integrating Europe into the Indian Ocean Trade by sailing around Africa. Chinese Admiral Zheng was also traveling far and wide in the largest wooden ships ever built. Columbus, whether portrayed as hero or villain, is generally credited as the great sailor of the 15th century, but he was not the only contender. What better way to settle this question than with a knock-down, drag-out, no holds barred, old-fashioned battle royal? We were going to make it a match cage, but welding is good.

Duration: 10:38

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NjEGncridoQ>

Zheng He 郑和下西洋 Episode 01 (Animados) CHINAnimax Vid

Date: October 2, 2012, (32,842 views)

Synopsis: Six hundred years ago, before Columbus sailed to the New World (the Americas) and long before Magellan circumnavigated the Earth, the Chinese emperor Yongle (Zhu Di) of the Ming dynasty ordered a vast fleet of ships to set sail for the western seas (we now call the Indian Ocean) to extend his imperial influence. Zheng He was placed as the admiral in control of the navy and army that undertook the many expeditions. Zheng He was one of the greatest sailors and explorers in history, a great diplomat, and a true hero.

Duration: 22:01

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6ncVxLoH4iM>

Zheng He 郑和下西洋 Episode 02 (Animados)

Date: October 3, 2012, (10,588 views)

Duration: 22:01

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KU9plFw8wDs>

Zheng He 郑和下西洋 Episode 03 (Animados)

Date: October 2, 2012 (11,975 views)
Duration: 22:01
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q24ML8O-R0s>

Great Voyages: Zheng He.
[Grandes viajes: Zhen He].
Date: October 10, 2013 (32,765 views)
Duration: 48:36
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=le7r93whykg>

Zheng He's Art of Collaboration: Pt 1. Explorer and manager.
[El arte de la colaboración de Zheng He: Pt 1. Explorador y gerente].
Date: March 11, 2014 (10,133 views)
Synopsis: 15th century Chinese admiral Zheng He (Cheng Ho) led the largest fleet the world has ever seen on seven epic voyages of discovery and trade from China to the east coast of Africa. This three-part series examines the leadership skills he needed and the many lessons still relevant to today's business leaders.
Duration: 9:02
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lXZxQmWdgA0>

Canned Histories: The Voyages of Zheng He.
[Historias enlatadas: Los viajes de Zheng He].
Fecha: 30 de mayo de 2014 (18.617 visualizaciones)
Synopsis: Details the life and adventures of one of the world's greatest explorers: Zheng He. Zheng doesn't get as much credit as his European counterparts, mostly because he didn't colonize the lands he visited, exploit the native peoples for their land and resources, or do the patented Spanish "dance of conquest" for all their tombs and places of worship. Shouldn't he be more revered for not doing those things?
Duration: 10:58
Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RvYcQB_y4Zk

Zheng He's Floating City: When China Dominated the Oceans.
[Zheng He y su ciudad flotante: cuando China dominó los océanos].
Date: September 4, 2014. (604,142 views)
Duration: 18:16
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t-s1K56UgM0>

Zheng He, Empereur Des Mers - Partie 1/4.
[Zheng He, emperador de los mares – Parte 1/4].
Date: October 3, 2014 (5,193 views)
Synopsis: Documentary film about the history of China, tracing the journey of the Emperor of the Seas - "Zheng He". Film produced by Bang Singapore.
Duration: 14:07

Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=es__Le3eob0

Zheng He, Empereur Des Mers - Partie 2/4.

[Zheng He, emperador de los mares – Parte 2/4].

Date: October 3, 2014 (2,198 views)

Duration: 14:01

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6V7mIyfPL1s>

Zheng He, Empereur Des Mers - Partie 3/4.

[Zheng He, emperador de los mares – Parte 3/4].

Date: October 3, 2014 (1,812 views)

Duration: 13:53

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tFe89wpGPAQ>

Zheng He, Empereur Des Mers - Partie 4/4.

[Zheng He, emperor of the seas - Part 4/4].

Date: October 3, 2014 (1,635 views).

Duration: 10:05

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=maqA7ISSHmI>

Les voyages de l'amiral Chinois musulman Zheng He - 1/2.

[Los viajes del almirante chino-musulmán Zheng He – 1/2].

Date: September 30, 2015 (15,363 views). Synopsis: Mahmoud Shams oud-Din (Tshengh Kheh / Zheng He) is a Chinese Muslim eunuch, working for the Ming dynasty emperor then in power in China in the early 9th century Hegirian (15th century Gregorian). The emperor made him admiral of the imperial fleet. Mahmoud Shams oud-Din organized large exploration expeditions in the Indian Ocean. In 808 H. (1405 G.), he embarked on a maritime expedition during which he traveled the world on seven voyages. He reached Indonesia, India, Arabia and Africa and brought samples of local wildlife back to China. Ma Huan, another Chinese Muslim, accompanied the admiral on several of his voyages to the west. It was he who wrote the account of the imperial fleet's expeditions, sharing his observations on geography, laws, politics, climatic conditions, environment, economy, local customs... of the countries visited. Some claim that Mahmoud Shams oud-Din's expeditions passed Mozambique, bypassed the Cape of Good Hope and even reached America.

Duration: 56:45

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=An8KfWQxZTI>

Les voyages de l'amiral Chinois musulman Zheng He - 2/2.

[The voyages of the Chinese-Muslim admiral Zheng He - 2/2].

Date: October 1, 2015 (5,361 views).

Duration: 56:59

Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AVWgjW_c-D4

A photographic exhibition traces the travels of Marco Polo and Zheng He.
Date: March 21, 2016 (122 views) CCTV News (Photos by Michael Yamashita)
Duration: 2:55
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J056Ff6PsSM>

History Documentaries - Chinese Treasure Fleet Adventures of Zheng He Documentary.
Date: April 21, 2017 (9,518 views).
Duration: 1:33:28
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l00W-BaWAKU>

Un modelo de buque de la flota de Zheng He reproducido en Shanghái.
[A model ship from Zheng He's fleet reproduced in Shanghai].
Date: July 13, 2017 (367 views) China Xinhua English
Synopsis: The ship Ming Fu, from the Zheng He fleet, is reproduced at the Chinese Maritime Museum when China's Navigation Day.
Duration: 1:06
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=746bNDdD74E>

Imperio chino realizó expediciones navales mucho antes que Europa.
[Chinese empire carried out naval expeditions long before Europe].
Date: August 3, 2017 (616 views) teleSUR tv
Synopsis: The city of Nanjing was the ancient capital of the Chinese empire. During the 15th century, the Chinese navy was known for its large ships and the great voyages they made. These ships were manufactured in Nanjing, noted for making voyages long before those made by European colonists. Zheng He commanded the first naval expeditions and traveled through Asia and Africa in seven voyages, taking with him Chinese treasures such as porcelain and silk to exchange and make relations with other regions.
Duration: 3:12
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=slxc-xGCon8>

2006 01 18 Les Aventures Maritimes De L'amiral Eunuque Zheng He.
[2006 01 18 The maritime adventures of the eunuch admiral Zheng He].
Date: December 12, 2017 (5,048 views).
Duration: 10:05
Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ANILMU8FIos>

Epic voyages of Zheng He, 15th Century Chinese Admiral (1001 Inventions).
[Epic voyages of Zheng He, 15th century Chinese admiral (1001 inventions)].
Date: January 24, 2018 (8,534 views).
Synopsis: Between 1405 and 1433, the Ming government sponsored a series of seven naval expeditions. The emperor designed them to establish a Chinese presence, impose imperial control over trade, impress foreign peoples in the Indian

Ocean basin, and extend the empire's tributary system. Zheng He was the man chosen to lead this great fleet that reached as far as East Africa opening rich trade routes, bringing peace and prosperity to war-ravaged far-off lands, religious equality and China on the road to economic dominance over the rest of the world. Why did China suddenly stop the treasure fleets and close its borders to its newfound trading partners? Did the Chinese Muslim admiral, Zheng He, discover America before Columbus? Is this map the proof?

Duration: 2:33

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c28oBqNk8MM>

La Armada china misteriosos viajes del almirante Zheng en el S. XIV.

[The Chinese Navy mysterious voyages of Admiral Zheng in the 14th century]

Date: February 15, 2018 (61 views).

Duration: 1:46:36

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zpNwfXvneGk>

When China Ruled the Waves (Chinese Dynasty Documentary) | Timeline.

[Cuando China gobernó las olas (documental de la dinastía china) | línea del tiempo].

Date: March 1, 2018 (780,414 views)

Duration: 48:03

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h4YEADagu0o>

¿China descubrió América? Los viajes de Zheng He.

[Did China discover America? The travels of Zheng He].

Date: April 25, 2018 (44,177 views)

Duration: 12:16

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8ZH1HtcUmt4>

¿Quién llegó a América antes que Colón?

[Who arrived in America before Columbus?].

Date: April 26, 2018 (982,850 views) Academia Play

Synopsis: Pre-Columbian transoceanic contacts are the possible relationships existing between Native Americans and the inhabitants of other continents prior to the discovery of America in 1492, when Christopher Columbus arrived at the American continent.

Duration: 9:58

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xfZ2rmt0eZc>

Zheng He Voyage (Ming Treasure Fleet).

[Zheng He Voyage (Ming Treasure Fleet)].

Date: May 28, 2018 (37,414 views).

Duration: 17:21

Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=es__Le3eob0

Zhenghe (Chinese explorer): facts and his accomplishments, the untold story.

[Zhenghe (explorador chino): los hechos y sus logros, la historia inédita].

Date: October 2, 2018 (2,446 views) East Asian Cultures.

Synopsis: The wonderful story of Zheng He, the Chinese explorer, who led huge naval fleets on the oceans, 100 years before famous European sailors like Magellan and Bartolomeu Dias. Zheng He's ships, Zheng He's discoveries, Zheng He's achievements, what Zheng He discovered, are all parts of an incredible story that has not been told enough.

Running time: 3:08

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j6AafYnGJjI>

China (Los Viajes del Almirante Zheng He en el Siglo XV).

[China (The Voyages of Admiral Zheng He in the 15th Century)].

Date: October 17, 2018 (9,137 views) Megalopolis Channel

Synopsis: In the late 14th century, Emperor Zhu Di of the Ming dynasty possessed a gigantic fleet of ships and sent it under the command of Admiral Zheng He to the unknown world that stretched beyond the China Sea. Who was Zheng He? What was the purpose of these voyages?

Running time: 51:47

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IYME3NSWUb8>

The Voyages of Zheng He.

[Los viajes de Zheng He].

Date: November 24, 2018 (53,300 views).

Synopsis: 87 years before Christopher Columbus set sail for Spain to the "New World", a Muslim from China set sail for a new world. Columbus had 3 ships. This guy had 317, and some of his ships were twice as big as Columbus' ships. Columbus had a crew of 87. This guy had 30,000. Columbus traveled 4,000 miles (6400 km). This guy traveled 7,000 (11,000 km). And this guy didn't steal resources from foreign lands or take over these foreign lands like Columbus did. Instead, he gave nice gifts and brought people home to introduce them to his family. His name was Zheng He, and here is the story of his travels. In the early 1400s, China was the best dog in the world. This was when it was known as the Great Ming Empire, named after the ruling Ming dynasty. The third emperor of the Ming dynasty, Zhu Di aka the Yongle Emperor, wanted the world to know how strong China was. He had an aggressive foreign policy, leading military campaigns against Mongol tribes to the north and west. Di also brought back the traditional tribute system, which said that countries on China's borders had to recognize China as their boss and basically kiss his feet. These countries would give gifts to China, and in return China offered its protection and access to goods.

Duration: 9:21

Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1_Elh_jo_dc

Zheng He's voyages (1405-33).

[Viajes de Zheng He (1405-1433)].

Date: december 31, 2019 (1,127 views).

Synopsis: Zheng He (鄭和 1371-1433) was a Chinese sailor, explorer, diplomat, fleet admiral, and court official during the Ming dynasty. Zheng He commanded expeditionary voyages to Southeast Asia, South Asia, West Asia and East Africa in seven voyages from 1405 to 1433. His largest ships stretched 120 meters or more in length, carrying hundreds of sailors on four tiers of decks. Zheng He was born Ma He (馬和) into a Muslim family in Kunyang, Kunming, Yunnan, China. He had an elder brother and four sisters. Zheng was a great-great-grandfather of Sayyid Ajjal Shams al-Din Omar, who served in the administration of the Mongol Empire and was governor of Yunnan during the early Yuan dynasty.

Duration: 45:10

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LpXvqalkGDs>

Zheng He, la folle histoire du grand explorateur eunuque!

[Zheng He, the crazy story of the great eunuch explorer!]

Date: February 17, 2020 (287,170 views)

Synopsis: What if I told you that one of the most incredible explorers in history had never set foot on a ship before his emperor entrusted him with the crucial mission of developing his commercial and diplomatic network on the seas? This is the extraordinary fate of Admiral Zheng He, who led one of the largest exploration fleets in history!

Running time: 9:08

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0b2KCLc625A>